

REPORT:

A3.3.4 : Report on the geometry and dimension of microfluidic component ports.

Work package 3

This report was written as part of activity 3.3.4 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

This report was written by:

Huabing Yin	University of Glasgow	Huabing.yin@glasgow.ac.uk
Henne van Herren	EnablingMNT	henne@enablingmnt.com
Elsa Batista	IPQ	ebatista@ipq.pt
Fernanda Saraiva	IPQ	fsaraiva@ipq.pt
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	vsilverio@inesc-mn.pt
Kevin Romieu	CETIAT	kevin.romieu@cetiat.fr

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

Contents

1. Scope.....	3
2. Overview of the fabrication methods.....	3
2.1. Glass chips.....	3
2.2. Polymeric chips	3
3. Effects of fabrication methods on materials and interface	4
3.1. Glass chips.....	4
3.2. Plastic chips.....	5
4. Ports and connectors	7
4.1 Glass chips.....	8
4.2 Moulded plastic chips	9
5 Experimental results	10
5.1 PDMS chip, from INESC, assembled with different components	10
5.2 Topas chip (A), Microfluidic Chipshop, assembled with different components.....	11
5.3 Topas chip (C), Microfluidic Chipshop, assembled with different components.....	13
5.4 Dimensional measurements	14
6 Conclusions	18
7 References	19
Appendix 1: Examples of the layout of commercial glass chips	20
Appendix 2: Examples of commercial glass chips, connectors, and chip holders	22
Appendix 3: Flow measurement results for the 3 chips assembly using the gravimetric and the front track method.....	26

1. Scope

This document provides an overview of commonly used fabrication processes and post-treatments for glass and the identified top plastic materials, and the potential effects of these processes on materials' properties, microchannel structure, and chip-to-world connection and was developed based on the activity A3.3.4: Report on the geometry and dimension of microfluidic component ports.

In terms of the compatibility of microfluidic components with different sizes of the connection ports, we have looked only at commercially available devices and components.

2. Overview of the fabrication methods

Most microfluidic products are made from transparent materials. The report from 3.1.1 has identified the top five materials for microfluidic chips, including cyclic olefin copolymer (COC), cyclic olefin polymers (COP); polycarbonate (PC); polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), and Glass. The main fabrication methods for microfluidic devices from these materials are summarised below.

2.1. Glass chips

The glass and glass/silicon-based devices are created by wafer-scale processing in a similar way to the semiconductor industry: through lithographic processes, a structure is generated onto a glass or silicon wafer; following up processes, such as wet etching, dry etching, and/or powder blasting result in microfluidic channels and other structures (e.g., access holes). For glass/metal hybrid devices, additional processes, such as metallisation, are included between these steps.

Bonding glass wafers to form closed microfluidic devices can be done by fusion-, thermal-, adhesive or low-temperature bonding methods. Separating the whole wafer into individual devices is done via dicing. The advantages of glass processing are the accuracy of structuring, the durability of the devices and the transparency.

2.2. Polymeric chips

Polymeric microfluidic devices offer great flexibility and low cost compared to glass devices. They are often produced in one single step taking advantage of the thermal deformation or melting of the polymer. The most used fabrication processes are injection moulding, hot embossing or thermoforming. In injection moulding, powder or granular polymer is heated until it melts or becomes plastically formable. The polymeric mass is injected and compacted by a rotating screw under high pressure into a closed mould. The mould determines the shape and surface structure of the finished

part. Injection moulding is regarded as the most cost-efficient method for fabricating microfluidic parts in large quantities.

Embossing and thermoforming rely on the deformation of the polymer when submitted to heat and pressure. In these processes, a solid plate or sheet of the polymer is forced into an open cavity containing the mould and is pressed against the mould at a given temperature.

To form an enclosed microfluidic chip, the microfluidic substrate must be bonded to a cover plate. Thermal bonding of polymeric microchips has been the dominant method. However, other low-temperature methods, including adhesive, solvent bonding and surface modifications, have been explored to allow for the preservation of functioned surfaces. Bonding polymers with very small channels is difficult since the channel integrity and structure should not be altered during the process.

3. Effects of fabrication methods on materials and interface

The combination of the fabrication methods and material types can determine the smallest achievable dimension and surface roughness, which can affect the optical properties of the materials and the connection with other components. This section will overview the potential effects of the fabrication processes on both materials and structures.

3.1. Glass chips

Glass devices can withstand high pressure, organic solvents and thus have been widely used in synthesis and analysis [1]. The smallest achievable feature for glass devices depends on both the lithographic technique and etching steps used to fabricate it. For structures made by wet isotropic etching, the smallest channel width is the sum of the minimum photolithography resolution ($>1 \mu\text{m}$) and $2x$ etch depth. Normal etch depth is in the range of $(0.010-500) \mu\text{m}$. Consequently, for deep channels, the space between adjacent channels should consider the etch depth. Wet isotropic etching produces very low surface roughness ($<5\text{nm}$), which is one of its significant advantages (commercial device data) .

The Dry etch process requires fused silica and can produce a channel width as small as $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ if e-beam lithography is used. Typical depths for a conventional dry etch are below $40 \mu\text{m}$. Importantly, the width of the channel is independent of etch depth. Therefore, dry etching is the method of choice for submicron features or/and high aspect ratio channels. Since dry etching of glass produces high-energy ions that break Si-O bonds, it can lead to higher surface roughness compared to wet isotropic etching, normally in the range of $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Powder blasting is a fast and cheap technique but generates larger features, with a feature size accuracy of about 25 μm . The channel depth can reach 100 μm and more. The sides of the wells are not completely vertical but sloped at an angle (normally at 70°). Channels created by power blasting normally have high surface roughness over 6 μm [2, 3]. These can affect the optical detection of samples within the channel.

A rougher surface would cause adverse effects on the flow profile, optical transmission and reflection as well as promote bubble formation. Therefore, the surface is preferably as smooth as possible. Generally, optical detection is through the flat cover substrate and is not affected by the roughness of the sidewall. However, if optical detection is from the side of the channel, not only the surface roughness but also the slope angle of the channel can affect the optical detection, for example, by adding an undesirable lens effect.

Table 1: comparison of different fabrication methods for glass microfluidic devices

	wet etching	Dry etching	Powder blasting
Surface roughness	< 5 nm	<2.5 μm	>5 μm
Vertical wall	No	Yes	No
Aspect ratio (W/H)	Low	High	low
Smallest feature	> 1 μm	0.1 μm	> 25 μm
Effects on optical properties	minimum	minimum	High

In summary:

Fabrication of glass microfluidic devices requires both lithography and etching processes. The three most commonly used etching processes, namely wet isotropic etching, dry etching and powder blasting, have main differences in the resultant surface roughness, the slope of the sidewall, the aspect ratio of the channel, and the smallest feature size. Wet etching gives the smoothest surface and dry etching is the choice of method for submicron features. However, both require access to clean rooms. Powder blasting provides a fast and cheap method to fabricate large microfluidic channels for optically non-demanding applications.

3.2. Plastic chips

Polymers offer versatile material choices for microfluidic devices. Thermal plastic materials, including COC and COP, are most widely used for making microfluidic chips due to their rigid mechanical properties, low water uptake and excellent optical properties [4]. These materials have a distinct softening at a glass transition temperature (T_g), which makes them processable around this

temperature. Common fabrication methods for these materials include injection moulding, hot embossing, and nanoimprinting. Injection moulding is a choice for high volume production of devices (e.g., hundreds of thousands or millions) at low per-device cost, although it has a high initial set-up cost. Hot embossing is generally considered for low-middle volume production. In hot embossing, only a small portion of the substrate is embossed compared to the initial substrate thickness. In nanoimprinting, the entire or nearly the entire thickness of the polymer film is patterned and can fabricate COP structures with features in the nanometer range. Considering the importance of injection moulding in the manufacturing industry, this section will focus on the potential effects of the moulding processes and post-treatments on the materials and structure of the moulded devices.

3.2.1 Effects of the moulding process:

Injection moulding involves the following steps, 1) melting polymer at a temperature of the order of 200-350 °C (depending on the polymer), 2) injecting the polymer liquid into the mould under high pressure (typically between (600 and 1,000) bar), 3) solidify polymer by cooling and 4) demoulding. Since the material undergoes a phase change, internal stresses, shrinkage, and birefringence are usually high[5]. Shrinkage can cause many problems during demoulding, where the microstructure can be torn apart, deformed and destroyed. Non-uniformity of the shrinkage can also reduce shape stability, produce warpage, and affect the flatness of microfluidic chip. Previously, warpage, measured using a laser profilometer, was reported to influence micro-parts of the order of a few microns for a 3-mm length [6]. Thus, suitable designs of microstructures and moulding parameters should be carefully chosen.

3.2.2 Effects of encapsulation:

Currently, injection moulded structures are formed from two (1/2) structures and need to be assembled with the other polymer part to form closed microchannels. The most widely used method is adhesive materials, such as glue or heat/pressure adhesive tapes[7]. However, for channels with small dimensions, there is a risk of blockage by adhesive materials. If the adhesive layer is on the optical path, it will affect optical detection, for example, by altering light transmission and the refractive index of the substrate. Thermal pressure bonding is popular if the bottom and top plates are made from materials with slightly different glass transition temperatures (T_g). This is usually done by heating them above the T_g and pressing them together. However, since the operation window (i.e., the range of temperature and pressure is often narrow, there is also a risk of damaging the microstructure. Solvent bonding uses a suitable solvent to dissolve the material at the interface, which solidifies again after subsequent evaporation.

Similarly, microstructures can be damaged due to “melting” by solvent excess. Ultrasonic welding generates thermal energy by ultrasonically actuating mechanical movement of structures and can damage small-sized channels. It is apparent that the commonly used sealing methods all impose risks to altering microstructures. Therefore, it is important to measure the smallest dimensions that can be reliably achieved by each method [7].

3.2.3 Effects of post-treatment:

After the microfabrication of polymeric devices, one or more processing steps are needed to generate functional microfluidic devices. For applications that require electrodes, thin-film technologies of sputtering and evaporation or thick-film methods by screen printing using a paste of metal particles, are normally used. This process is preferably done at room temperature to avoid poor adhesion between metal and polymeric devices (caused by their different thermal expansion coefficients). Holes can be drilled mechanically or by laser ablation, but burrs could form during the drilling process, which prevents the bonding or connection to the other components [6]. However, injection moulding can also integrate fluidic interconnection or through holes on-chip - one of its significant advantages. (see examples below)

In summary:

This section focused on the polymeric microfluidic devices manufactured via injection moulding. The properties that are most affected by the moulding and the post-injection processes include:

- The dimension stability and accuracy of microstructures (e.g. altered structure due to shrinkage)
- The flatness of the substrate (e.g., due to warpage formation)
- Optical properties of the substrate (e.g., refractive index change due to adhesive layer)
- Holes and connection (e.g., burr formation)

4. Ports and connectors

Although several chip sizes are used for microfluidics, substantial numbers of commercial microfluidic devices have the exact outer dimensions of standard microscope slides and microtitrates. Apart from gluing connectors on a chip, glass chips often use clamping systems to connect to tubing; in contrast, moulded plastic devices often use mini-luers (Figure 1). This section introduces commonly used connectors, their size and location on commercial devices.

Figure 1. Overview of chip layout and connections for polymeric and glass devices.

4.1 Glass chips

Commercial glass chips often use clamped interconnections, either from the side or the top. Different companies have different sized chips and thus offer their clamp systems, which generally use a gasket (or O-ring) to form a tight seal (Figure 2). The chip can be held against the connector via different mechanisms, including 1) screw tightening, 2) magnet holding, 3) spring-loaded clamping, and 4) hooks. Several representative commercial examples are shown in Appendix 1. They are different in outer dimensions, spacing between ports, port size and tubing size.

An important advantage of clamped contacts compared to mini-luer based connections is the low dead volume of the microfluidic path and the ability to make several interconnections at the same time, for instance, by using Chip holders. Dead volume poses a detrimental threat in microfluidic operation as it creates regions where air bubbles or compressible gas can trap. These air pockets can lead to bubble release and flow pulsing due to the presence of compressible gas in the flow path.

Figure 2. Schematic drawing of clamped connectors. Left: top connection (Figure adapted from <https://www.mycorsolutions.com/fitting-and-connector-tutorial.html>). Right: side connector (adapted from <https://www.dolomite-microfluidics.com/>)

4.2 Moulded plastic chips

Most thermoplastic chips have dimensions of a standard microscope slide (75.5 mm x 25.5 mm x 1.5 mm) or microtiter plates (85.48 mm x 127.76 mm). Mini-luvers or Oliver ports are commonly used, as shown in Figure 3. They can be either glued on the chip or integrated on-chip during moulding – one of the big advantages of injection moulding. Mini-luvers are normally placed on the borders of the chip with a pitch of 4.5 mm (or 9 mm for luvers) according to the positions of the outer walls of the standard layout (Figure 4). The most common port size is 1.5 mm, which is normally linked with flexible tubing (e.g. silicone, Tygon) ($0.5 \text{ mm} < \text{ID} \leq 1.0 \text{ mm}$) or Silicone sleeve ($0.5 \text{ mm} < \text{ID} \leq 1.0 \text{ mm}$) plus rigid tubing (e.g. PTFE, PEEK) ($\text{OD} > \text{ID}$ of sleeve) (Figure 4 B and Figure 5). However, there is limited information on the choice of tubing for commonly used connectors and the tolerance of a combination for leak-free operation under different pressures.

(A)

(B)

Figure 3. Typical plastic chip with moulded connectors. (a) mini-luer and (B) Oliver port connectors. i)- layout of the chip and ii) dimension of port and spacing. Devices are from Microfluidic ChipShop (<https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com/>)

(A)

(B)

Figure 4: (A) dimension of a male Mini-Luer connector and (B) tubing connection to mini Luer. (Microfluidic ChipShop, <https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com/>)

Figure 5: Schematic drawing of typical parallel fluidics device with connector options highlighted from top to bottom, Luer, barbed fitting, threaded flat bottom fitting. It is adapted from Parallel Fluidics, <https://parallefluidics.com/>.

5 Experimental results

Several tests were performed to investigate the compatibility of various components from in 3 different chips assemblies, in order to ensure the traceability of dimensional measurements to primary standards.

5.1 PDMS chip, from INESC, assembled with different components

- a) Chip – 1 -PDMS with one channel of 100 μm width and 50 μm depth, with two 0.9 mm inlet holes; material: PDMS; dimensions: 40 x 10 mm; manufactured by INESC MN

b) Stainless steel catheter plug – (external diameter 0,9 mm X 12 mm long), Instech

c) Connecting tube – Polyethylene tube 59 cm long, 0,9 mm inner diameter, BTPE-90, Instech Laboratories

Assembly of all components

5.2 Topas chip (A), Microfluidic Chipshop, assembled with different components

Components from ChipShop:

- a) Chip A- 16 parallel channels with fluid interface holes, Material: TOPAS® (COC polymer for medical use), Dimensions: 75.5mm x 25.5mm x 1.5mm, with eight parallel channels of 100 μm width, 100 μm depth, 18 mm length; connectors are glued to the chip holes model 10000198, lote Z1112070.

b) Connector - Material: opaque polypropylene (PP), model 10000700 lote FA127725.

c) Large rubber tube - Material: silicone, Diameter: 0,76 mm (internal); 1,65 mm (external), model 10000031

Other components:

a) Stainless steel catheter plug – (external diameter 0,9 mm X 12 mm long) , Instech

b) Connecting tube – Polyethylene tube 59 cm long, 0,9 mm inner diameter, BTPE-90, Instech Laboratories

Assembly of all components

5.3 Topas chip (C), Microfluidic Chipshop, assembled with different components

Components from ChipShop:

- a) Chip C- 16 parallel channels with mini luer fluidic interface, Material: TOPAS® (COC polymer for medical use), Dimensions: 75.5mm x 25.5mm x 4mm, with eight parallel channels of 100 μm width, 100 μm depth, 18 mm length. Luer fluidic interface, similar to “female mini luer port” integrated directly on the chip, model 10000168, lote J1125176.

- b) Connector - Material: opaque polypropylene (PP), model 10000094, Lote FF115266

Other components:

- a) Stainless steel catheter plugs – (external diameter 0,9 mm X 12 mm long) , Instech

- b) Connecting tube – Polyethylene tube 59 cm long, 0,9 mm inner diameter, BTPE-90, Instech Laboratories

Assembly of all components

5.4 Dimensional measurements

The dimensions of all chips components were measured by a Machine of three-dimensional optical measurement (3D MMO) or profile projector, brand Mitutoyo Quick Vision, resolution 0,0001 mm. This equipment includes a computational application – Mitutoyo Mitac Qvpack, version 7.401A – that ensures the virtual construction of geometric elements (lines, circles, among others) necessary for the measurement of dimensional and geometric quantities of interest. In addition, it has its own artificial lighting system adjustable to the observation of opaque objects and translucent with differentiated photometric characteristics.

Figure 6: Three-dimensional optical measuring machine

Also, measurements were performed by an interferometer from HP, model 5528A, resolution 0,00001 mm.

Figure 7: Interferometer setup

The results are the following:

Chip PDMS dimensions measured with an interferometer

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
PE Tube	Inner diameter	1,26 mm	0,04

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Stainless steel catheter	External diameter	0,912 mm	0,010

	Measurand	Value	SD/mm
Hole in the chip	Inner diameter	0,710 mm	0,003

Chip A dimensions measured interferometry

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
PE Tube	Inner diameter	1,26 mm	0,040

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Stainless steel catheter	External diameter	0,912 mm	0,010

	Measurand	Value	SD/mm
Ruber tube	Inner diameter	0,806 mm	0,005

Chip A dimensions measured with 3D machine

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Ruber tube	Inner diameter	0,820 mm	0,039

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Connector	External diameter top	1,77 mm	0,44

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Hole in the Chip	Inner diameter	1,384 mm	0,038

Chip C dimensions measured interferometry

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
PE Tube	Inner diameter	1,26 mm	0,040

	Measurand	Value	<i>U</i> /mm
Stainless steel catheter	External diameter	0,912 mm	0,010

	Measurand	Value	<i>SD</i> /mm
Connector	Small inner diameter	0,93 mm	0,11
	Big external diameter	2,577 mm	0,012

	Measurand	Value	<i>SD</i> /mm
Hole in the chip	Inner diameter	2,883 mm	0,007

Chip C dimensions measured with 3D machine

	Measurand	Value	U /mm
Connector	Big external diameter	2,78 mm	0,18

	Measurand	Value	U /mm
Hole in the chip	Inner diameter	2,843 mm	0,019

Discussion

In the length measurements, the measured values (estimation of the length measurands) and the uncertainties obtained with the two methods used: interferometer and profile projector, are compatible.

By interferometry, due to the available equipment, the definition of the measuring plane of the accessories in translucent material, presented technical difficulty. For these measurements, only the standard deviation of the measurements was indicated.

Shape deviations intrinsic to the accessories (roundness, cylindricity) of the plastic material are identified as the main factors for the high value of the standard deviation found (of the order of 0.01 mm, when the interferometer has a resolution of 0.01 μm).

The shape deviations and the plasticity of the constituent material of the tubes and connectors prevent measurement with superior accuracy, when we use the interferometer as measuring equipment to guarantee the metrological traceability of these accessories.

With the profile projector it was possible to calculate the uncertainties obtained and images of all accessories, even the translucent ones.

It can be verified that on the C chip that the outer diameter of the connector is smaller than the inner diameter of the hole in the chip and this means that this components are not compatible and may lead to leakage.

Flow tests were performed in each chip assembly using the front track method and the gravimetric method. The results are in Appendix 3 and confirm the connection problem in chip C where a leakage can be found in both methods.

6 Conclusions

For the fabrication of glass microfluidic devices, photolithography coupled with wet isotropic etching is the most widely used method. It has a distinct advantage in generating a smooth surface ($< 5 \text{ nm}$)

but is unsuitable for making submicron features and vertical sidewalls. Thermal bonding is the method of choice for making enclosed chips for high-pressure applications. Attention should be paid to the adhesive bonding method, which may affect the optical properties of the substrate.

For fabricating devices made from COC and COP, injection moulding is the method for high throughput manufacturing of devices at a low cost per device. However, the process parameters could alter microstructures and the flatness of the substrate.

Regarding compatibility between different microfluidic components, glass chips don't have standardised dimensions, the layout of port distribution and port size. Each company has its own design and clamping systems for external connections. In contrast, injection moulded COC/COP devices appear to be more uniform, mainly having the outer dimensions of a standard microscope slide or microtiter plate, 1.5 mm port size, and mini-luvers with a pitch of 4.5. It is usually connected to flexible tubing (or sleeve).

Recommendation for metrological measurements:

- Measure the dimensions of a microfluidic channel to evaluate the stability and accuracy of the microstructures (especially for injection moulded devices) using the appropriated methods.
- Measure the flatness of injection moulded devices.
- If an enclosed device is formed using an adhesive layer, measure changes in optical transmission, reflection, autofluorescence .
- Measure the diameter and tolerance of tubing that can form a tight fit under different pressures.

7 References

1. Oosterbroek, R.E., et al., *Fabrication and mechanical testing of glass chips for high-pressure synthetic or analytical chemistry*. Microsystem Technologies-Micro-and Nanosystems-Information Storage and Processing Systems, 2006. **12**(5): p. 450-454.
2. Solignac, D., et al., *Powder blasting for the realisation of microchips for bio-analytic applications*. Sensors and Actuators a-Physical, 2001. **92**(1-3): p. 388-393.
3. Huang, C.F., et al. *THE MICROCHANNEL OF MICROFLUIDIC CHIP FABRICATION BY MICRO-POWDER BLASTING*. in *12th International Symposium on Advances in Abrasive Technology*. 2009. Gold Coast, AUSTRALIA.
4. Nunes, P.S., et al., *Cyclic olefin polymers: emerging materials for lab-on-a-chip applications*. Microfluidics and Nanofluidics, 2010. **9**(2-3): p. 145-161.

5. Hecke, M. and W.K. Schomburg, *Review on micro molding of thermoplastic polymers*. Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering, 2004. **14**(3): p. R1-R14.
6. Attia, U.M., S. Marson, and J.R. Alcock, *Micro-injection moulding of polymer microfluidic devices*. Microfluidics and Nanofluidics, 2009. **7**(1): p. 1-28.
7. Becker, H. and C. Gartner, *Polymer microfabrication technologies for microfluidic systems*. Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry, 2008. **390**(1): p. 89-111.
8. Batista, E., Alves e Sousa J., Cardoso, S., Silverio, V., (2020), "Experimental testing for metrological traceability and accuracy of liquid microflows and microfluidics", Flow Measurement and Instrumentation, 71,101691
9. Batista, E., Sousa, J. A., Alvares, M., Afonso, J., Martins, R., (2021), "Development of an experimental setup for micro flow measurement using the front tracking method", Measurement: Sensors, 18, 100152

Appendix 1: Examples of the layout of commercial glass chips

Table A1: The dimension and port size, and layout of different glass chips

Chip dimension L-W-H (mm)	Spacing (mm)	Port Size (mm)	Connectors	tubing	Company
75.5-25.5- 1.5	4.5	N/A	Chipshop handling platform or using glue	Flexible tubing (0.5 mm < ID ≤ 1.0 mm)	Chipshop
75.5-25.5- 1.5	3	0.5-3.0	MBE212 fitting (ID: 1.0 mm, OD: 2.0 mm)	Flexible tubing (1.5 mm < ID ≤ 2.0 mm)	Ufluidic
45-15-X	5	Tapered, 1.56 to 0.9	Connect PRO chip holder + FFKM ferrules	ETFE (ID 0.25 mm/OD 1/16") or Fused silica (ID: 0.15 mm OD: 0.36- 0.375)	Micronit

29.8-22.3-3	3	0.5	linear connector	PTFE/ PEEK tubing (OD:1.6 mm)	Dolomite
15-15-2 (4 port) 30-15-4.1 (8 port)	3	0.4	linear connector	PTFE/PEEK tubing (OD:1.6 mm)	Dolomite

Microfluidic ChipShop (<https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com/>)

Fabrication: “Wet chemical etching is a suitable technology for structuring glass, but in addition to that, direct laser structuring, powder or sandblasting as well as photostructuring can be chosen according to the requirements.”

Bonding: not listed

(A)

(B)

Figure A1. (A) Typical glass ChipShop device (Listed as Chamber Chip - Fluidic 1075 & 1195 on ChipShop website) and schematic diagram and (B) Chipshop handling Platform (LOC-CCI 1):

Dolomite Microfluidics (<https://www.dolomite-microfluidics.com/>)

Fabrication: Wet etching, 100 nm to 1 mm channel depth, 5 nm surface roughness.

Bonding: Thermal Bonding

Figure A2. Pictures of dolomite linear connector for devices with ports on top (left) and side (right) of the device.

Figure A3. Plan view of port positioning for devices with top ports on dolomite chips for 8 and 12 port designs.

Micronit (<https://www.micronit.com/>)

Fabrication: “Structuring of glass is mostly done by etching (deep reactive ion etching, wet etching, powder blasting) and laser drilling”

Bonding: Direct/fusion bonding and Laser-assisted room temperature bonding

(A)

(B)

Figure A4. (A) Schematic drawing and picture of typical Micronit side connect device (B) the side connector with a device.

(A)

(B)

Figure A5. (A) Schematic drawing and picture of typical Micronit top connect device and (B) picture of the Micronit top connect device in cartridge (black) and Micronit Fluidic Connect PRO chip holder (blue).

Appendix 3: Flow measurement results for the 3 chips assembly using the gravimetric and the front track method.

Chip	Nominal Flow (mL/h)	Gravimetric method		
		Measured Out Flow of Chip (mL/h)	Error [%]	<i>U</i> (%)
PDMS	0,001	0,0011	11,94	25
	0,01	0,0107	4,84	4,1
	0,1	0,0907	8,17	2,5
	1	0,8875	0,55	2,4
A	0,01	0,0099	-1,0	5,0
	0,1	0,0983	-1,7	3,8
	1	0,9907	-0,93	0,19
C	0,01	0,0069	-31	5
	0,1	0,0970	-2,6	3,4
	1	1,0170	1,7	3,0

Figure A6 – Gravimetric flow setup

Chip	Nominal Flow (mL/h)	Front track method		
		Measured Out Flow of Chip (mL/h)	Error [%]	U (%)
PDMS	0,001	-0,0014	241,3	14,0
	0,01	0,0113	-13,3	3,3
	0,1	0,0961	3,9	2,6
	1	1,0257	-2,6	4,0
A	0,01	0,0095	5,0	3,7
	0,1	0,0967	3,3	2,8
	1	0,9819	1,8	6,2
C	0,01	-0,0033	133,0	43
	0,1	0,0996	0,4	1,9
	1	1,0259	-2,6	4,0

Figure A7 – Front track flow setup